

1 **An Empirical Investigation on the Use of Building Handover Information and its Quality**
2 **Requirements for Commercial Building Management**

3
4 **Abstract**

5 **Purpose:** Global building failures, such as the Grenfell Tower fire in London, UK, emphasised
6 the need for trustworthy building handover information for safety. However, a notable gap
7 remains in understanding how reliable handover information can ensure the safety of occupants.
8 This study investigates the use and the essential quality of handover information to understand
9 the effects of the quality of information on the management of commercial buildings.

10
11 **Design/methodology/approach:** Ninety-four participants from nine organisations who regularly
12 use handover information to manage multiple commercial buildings participated in the semi-
13 structured interviews. Qualitative thematic coding using interview transcripts was performed to
14 identify the utilisation of handover information and its quality requirements.

15
16 **Findings:** The study reveals that as-built drawings and product information are predominately
17 used to fulfil statutory obligations, comply with the organisation’s internal policies, evaluate
18 asset valuation, and make informed decisions about capital investment and operating expenses.
19 The quality dimensions of ‘Accuracy’, ‘Timeliness’, and ‘Completeness’ are preferred in
20 combination to achieve desired outcomes.

21
22 **Research limitations/implications:** This study focused on using handover information in the
23 management of commercial buildings. However, its results can offer valuable perspectives for
24 improving its application across various sectors in the built environment.

25
26 **Practical implications:** The findings affirm the need for quality handover information for
27 safety, compliance, and efficient management in commercial buildings.

28
29 **Original/value:** This research significantly contributes to the current knowledge of handover
30 information in the building sector. Given the study findings, building owners are equipped to
31 define specific handover information requirements and quality requisites.

32

33 **Keywords:** Building handover information, information quality dimensions, quality

34 deterioration, asset management, commercial buildings

35

36 **1. Introduction**

37

38 Various catastrophic building failures, including the Grenfell Tower fire in London, UK,
39 have brought attention to the urgent and critical need for reliable and trustworthy building
40 handover information in building management. Investigations into these failures have
41 emphasised the importance of maintaining quality handover information to ensure occupants'
42 safety (UK, 2022). In response, certain countries like the UK have enacted legislation requiring
43 asset owners to uphold credible and valid handover information throughout the post-construction
44 phase (Hackitt, 2018). In this context, the events surrounding the management of handover
45 information have significantly altered the general understanding of its role in building
46 management. While handover information has traditionally been utilised for routine
47 maintenance and operational support, its intended use beyond these areas remains unclear, and a
48 lack of clarity hampers the realisation of the full value and potential of managing handover
49 information. To fill this knowledge gap, it is essential to clarify the purpose and potential
50 applications of handover information and its quality requirements to manage buildings
51 comprehensively.

52 Handover information encompasses essential details about building projects, delivered in
53 graphical and non-graphical formats. Graphical information typically consists of as-built
54 drawings, while non-graphical information includes product details, operation and maintenance
55 manuals, warranty certificates and other relevant information (Kassem *et al.*, 2015; Chang *et al.*,
56 2022). The quality and specific requirements for handover information, particularly for its
57 intended use, remain debated. Previous studies have proposed diverse approaches to identify
58 building handover information requirements based on organisational needs, building types, and
59 practical necessities for operational needs (Rotimi *et al.*, 2015; Zhu *et al.*, 2021). However,
60 research gaps on the application of handover information have resulted in inconclusive findings.
61 High-quality handover information is essential to minimise the financial consequences of poor
62 quality, but contentious debates and lack of clarity in its use, especially in Building Information
63 Modelling (BIM)-based projects, present ongoing challenges.

64 The recent proliferation of Building Information Modelling (BIM) adoption in the
65 Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry presents an opportunity to deliver a
66 large volume of reliable handover information. BIM improves data exchange in the project
67 delivery phase, resulting in a quality collection of dependable information. However, the widely

68 acclaimed benefits of BIM depend on identifying the information requirements to optimise post-
69 construction support (Parn *et al.*, 2016) BIM can produce extensive digital project information at
70 an unprecedented rate. Yet, unclear information requirements may lead asset owners to
71 inefficiently navigate and potentially lose valuable information (Munir *et al.*, 2019). BIM-based
72 projects often provide handover information in unconventional formats, but their core
73 information requirements remain largely unchanged. Previous studies indicate that asset owners
74 have a ‘catch-all’ approach due to a lack of specific information requirements for building
75 management processes (Becerik-Gerber *et al.*, 2012; P. A. Zadeh *et al.*, 2017; Munir *et al.*, 2020)

76 This research, therefore, aims to address the following research objectives by conducting
77 an empirical investigation to enhance the understanding of the role of handover information:

- 78 1. Identify the use of building handover information to support the management of
79 commercial buildings and
- 80 2. Identify key information quality attributes that align with the desired outcomes of
81 commercial building management.

82 Ninety-four participants from nine organisations managing portfolios of commercial
83 buildings participated in semi-structured interviews. This approach is strategically chosen to
84 gather evidence-based insights into the use of handover information and its quality requirements
85 from the user’s perspective, which is essential for yielding the desired outcomes.

86 This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant studies on handover
87 information requirements and quality in supporting building management. Section 3 outlines the
88 participant selection, data collection and analysis. Section 4 presents the findings derived from
89 interviews. Section 5 discusses the significance of these findings. Finally, the paper concludes
90 with a summary of key takeaways, theoretical and practical contributions, limitations of the
91 study, and suggested paths for future research.

92 **2. Literature Review**

93 This section presents an overview of the literature review, focusing on the use of
94 handover information and its quality requirements in commercial building operations. A narrative
95 approach was adopted to synthesise key literature pertinent to this study selectively (Greenhalgh
96 *et al.*, 2018). A comprehensive literature search was conducted using Scopus and Web of Science
97 databases. Additionally, relevant industry publications were consulted, including International
98 Organization Standards (ISO) 8000 series: Data Quality, ISO 19650: Building Information

99 Modelling, and ISO 55000: Asset Management. This study also referenced the six primary
100 dimensions for data quality assessment established by Data Management (DAMA), UK.

101 *2.1. The management of commercial buildings in a built environment*

102 The management of complex-built assets such as commercial buildings involves a
103 comprehensive approach beyond routine maintenance and daily operational support. ISO 55000
104 outlines asset management guiding principles, value realisation, business alignment, leadership,
105 quality assurance and compliance with legislative requirements and organisational policies or
106 sector regulations (The International Organization for Standardization, 2014). External
107 compliance is key for safety and requires following specific requirements and practices,
108 including periodic mandated inspections and testing of various assets within a building, such as
109 electrical fixed wiring and equipment integrity inspections (The Institute of Asset Management,
110 2015). However, understanding the specific statutory compliance requirements can be
111 challenging, complicated by limited and handover information, which can vary by location.

112 *2.2. Handover information and its requirements*

113 Appendix 1 illustrates various handover information categories for a typical commercial
114 building project, though its effectiveness remains to be conclusively determined. Recently, ISO
115 19650 Part 3 outlined the practical applications of handover information in the post-construction
116 phase, underscoring its supportive role (International Organization for Standardization, 2020).
117 Additionally, Liu *et al.* (1994) highlighted the significance of floor plans and design
118 specifications in operational support, the criticality of spatial information related to door
119 locations and the identification of rooms and equipment. Becerik-Gerber *et al.* (2012)
120 emphasised the need for non-geometric information, such as manufacturing data, operational
121 instruction, maintenance specifications, and warranty information. Mayo and Issa (2016) noted
122 the high value of key product information related to fire, life and safety and HVAC systems.
123 Moreover, identifying handover information requirements involves considering factors such as
124 organisational needs, operational requirements, contractual obligations, building types, and asset
125 groups (East *et al.*, 2013; Cavka *et al.*, 2015; Farghaly *et al.*, 2018; Pishdad-Bozorgi *et al.*, 2018;
126 Munir *et al.*, 2020). However, the integration of regulatory perspectives into these requirements
127 remains unaddressed.

128 *2.3. Information quality*

129 Information quality is defined as its ability to meet end-user expectations and needs
130 (Wang and Strong, 1996; English, 1999; DAMA International, 2017). The widely accepted
131 definition implies that users determine quality attributes based on the information's intended use
132 (Wang and Strong, 1996; Strong, Lee and Wang, 1997; Pringle *et al.*, 2002). Information
133 commonly refers to processed data; different information can be produced using the same data –
134 the raw material of information – to fit a particular use (Mingers, 1996; DAMA International,
135 2017). This dynamic nature means it can become outdated yet remain reusable without losing its
136 value (Eaton and Bawden, 1991; Redman, 1995). Managing information involves efficient and
137 effective accessing, processing, and using information efficiently and effectively to meet the
138 organisational objectives throughout the information lifecycle, including creation, acquisition,
139 organisation, storage, distribution, and use (DAMA International, 2017).

140 Given the characteristics of information, various approaches developed frameworks for
141 defining quality attributes due to the established correlation between information quality and
142 business performance outcomes (Wang and Strong, 1996; English, 1999; DAMA International,
143 2017; He *et al.*, 2022). Wang and Strong (1996) proposed four categories of information quality
144 and relevant dimensions from the end user's perspective: intrinsic (accuracy and objectivity),
145 contextual (relevancy, timeliness, and completeness), representational (interpretability and
146 consistency), and accessibility (access security). English (1999) classified the characteristics
147 into two broad categories: (1) Inherent and (2) Pragmatic aspects. Inherent characteristics are
148 definitional conformity, complete values, validity, accuracy, precision, non-duplication,
149 equivalent redundant or distributed data, and concurrent redundant or distributed data. Pragmatic
150 characteristics include the presentation of data quality that meets the user's needs, such as
151 accessibility, timeliness, contextual clarity, usability, derivation integrity, and rightness or fact
152 completeness. Combining these approaches, DAMA UK (2013) published the six primary
153 quality dimensions:

- 154 • Completeness: All required information is available to meet the needs of the users.
- 155 • Uniqueness: Information is not duplicated in any records.
- 156 • Timeliness: All information is updated and current for the given task.
- 157 • Validity: All information follows their pre-defined syntax, including format and type.
- 158 • Accuracy: Information correctly reflects its real value.
- 159 • Consistency: No discrepancies exist when comparing multiple sets of information.

160 Therefore, this study adopts the DAMA's six core quality dimensions to analyse the preferred
161 quality characteristics of handover information.

162 Inevitably, the pursuit of information quality has extended to augment the diverse and
163 specialised handover information needed for the long-sophisticated phase of the building. The
164 case study by Cavka *et al.* (2015) examined the accuracy, reusability, and accessibility of
165 handover information. Thabet and Lucas (2017) highlighted the need to validate the
166 completeness and correctness of handover information to confirm confidence in its quality.
167 Similarly, Becerik-Gerber *et al.* (2012) and Bayar *et al.* (2016) stressed accuracy and
168 accessibility. Provided that the design quality can influence the quality of handover information,
169 Zadeh *et al.* (2017) evaluated the design quality in terms of completeness, accuracy, consistency,
170 compliance, and understandability. These studies offer a broad spectrum of quality requirements
171 but lack alignment with the ISO 8000 series framework for evaluating data quality. As such,
172 additional research is necessary to identify the appropriate quality preferences that effectively
173 cater to the multifaceted activities involved in building management.

174 This literature review of this study discusses three main topics: (1) commercial building
175 management in the built environment, (2) handover information and its requirements, and (3) the
176 relevant information quality framework. The reviews uncovered several gaps in knowledge.
177 Firstly, there is a lack of clarity on the specific information needed for legal compliances and
178 internal policies in commercial building operations. Secondly, diverse definitions of handover
179 information requirements exist, requiring consolidated interpretations from standard guidelines
180 to clarify their usage and scope. Thirdly, studies have yet to identify specific handover
181 information quality requirements to support the post-construction phase. Consequently, further
182 research is imperative to deepen the comprehension of handover information usage and its
183 quality attributes. This study aims to investigate the intended use of different classifications of
184 handover information and their practical application. The subsequent section will discuss the
185 exploration of the use and quality requirements of handover information.

186 **3. Methodology**

187 This study adopted an exploratory approach to investigate handover information's use and
188 quality dimensions in commercial building management. A rich and real-world context was
189 essential, requiring input from participants regularly using this information in their daily work.
190 Participants from nine organisations managing commercial buildings were selected. It is

191 important to note that the scope of this study is limited to the handover information utilisation in
192 commercial buildings and did not include residential buildings, infrastructure, healthcare, or
193 industrial properties.

194 *3.1. Sampling and recruitment*

195 The researcher utilised purposive sampling to recruit participants from nine organisations
196 that shared similar asset management settings in the US, UK, Northern Ireland, Germany, and
197 Ireland, all managing commercial buildings. This strategic selection aimed to accurately
198 represent the population to gain insightful information from participants' lived experiences,
199 focusing on those with 5 to 23 years of professional experience. Despite initial declines,
200 additional participants fitting the criteria were recruited using the snowball sampling technique
201 (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). These participants, currently managing construction projects, provided
202 valuable insights into the quality of handover information delivered from contractors. Table 1
203 summarises the participants and their areas of expertise.

204

205 **Table 1. List of Participants.**

206

207 *3.2. Data collection*

208 This study selected semi-structured interviews over surveys to collect relevant data.
209 Interviews were deemed appropriate for this study because lengthy, semi-structured interviews
210 provide first-hand experience from participants in organic ways. Semi-structured interviews
211 effectively uncover professional insights and tacit knowledge on the topic under investigation.
212 These interviews allowed participants to express their perspectives. Interviewing continued until
213 saturation was reached, a point where no new information emerged from the participants (Fusch
214 and Ness, 2015).

215 Interview questions were pre-defined into four categories to facilitate specific data
216 extraction: (1) characteristics of buildings, (2) handover information processes and sources, (3)
217 desired information quality dimensions, and (4) handover information management using asset
218 information management tools. Participants described the current handover information usage,
219 highlighting the challenges and limitations of timely access to the correct information. They
220 shared their preferred information quality dimensions for the essential information, drawing from
221 their experiences. Participants had the discretion to abstain from answering sensitive questions.

222 The average length of the interview process was approximately 60 minutes. Each interview was
223 recorded and transcribed with the permission of the participants.

224 3.3. Data analysis

225 This study analysed interview data using qualitative thematic analysis steps outlined by
226 Gioia *et al.* (2013). The initial step involved capturing participants' quotes and phrases
227 describing their experience of using different classifications of handover information for the
228 selected asset management process within the boundaries of each participant's job
229 responsibilities. Block diagrams were created to acquaint the existing asset management
230 processes. Concurrently, first-order descriptive codes were developed from each interview
231 transcript. By performing the data reduction process, these first-order categories were further
232 clustered into broader discussion topics to improve understanding of the use of building
233 handover information (Gioia *et al.*, 2013; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2021). Before performing a
234 complete analysis, codes were adjusted to maintain data objectively, enhancing the reliability and
235 validity of the final (Weber, 1990).

236 During the interviews, participants detailed their desired quality attributes of handover
237 information, with a notable emphasis on 'Accuracy'. Only a few participants articulated the
238 ranking of the quality dimensions. To ensure unified results, the terminology of information
239 quality dimensions was aligned: 'Correctness' or 'Correct information' was considered
240 'Accuracy'. Similarly, 'Up-to-date' information was deemed for 'Timeliness'. Finally,
241 'Usability' and 'Availability' were judged as 'Completeness', following the definition defined by
242 the DAMA. The data, encompassing varied quality attributes, was organised in a spreadsheet,
243 following the six primary quality dimensions established by DAMA (UK DAMA, 2013).
244 Additionally, radar charts were used to highlight outliers and commonalities in the reported
245 quality attributes, displaying the average frequency reported of each dimension. Chosen for their
246 ability to succinctly exhibit relationships and patterns among multiple variables, making it an
247 effective visual presentation, though they are illustrative and lack statistical significance (Henry,
248 1995; Saary, 2008).

249 Adopting a systematic thematic process facilitated the identification and comparison of
250 emergent themes from each participant's narrative and descriptive interview data, leading to
251 meaningful insights. This study explored raw data from asset management professionals to

252 provide explanatory information that could increase understanding of the use of handover
253 information in commercial building management.

254 4. Findings

255 This section presents the identified use of building handover information with the quality
256 preferences. The findings were derived from qualitative thematic analysis of interviews,
257 supported by anonymous quotes from participants identified, such as ID 1 and ID 2, to preserve
258 confidentiality. The research indicates that handover information is used to comply with the
259 organisation’s internal compliance requirements and legal obligations, in addition to ongoing
260 asset valuation, capital investment, and decision support for recurring operating expenditures.
261 Table 2 presents a summary of the use of handover information derived from interview findings.
262 These results have been aligned with the discussion topic for an in-depth analysis, offering
263 insights into the application of handover information in commercial building management, as
264 illustrated in Figure 1.

265

266 **Table 2. Use of Handover Information for Commercial Building Operations.**

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269

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Figure 1. Mapping of the Interview Results to Discussion Topics.

271

Source: Authors’ own creation/work.

272

273 *4.1. Asset lifecycle delivery*

274 Asset lifecycle delivery involves a series of activities aimed at managing the entire
275 lifecycle of a building. The Institute of Asset Management (IAM) emphasises the significance of
276 meeting compliance-related obligations as part of the lifecycle delivery process, as operating a
277 building is subject to various statutory compliance requirements (The Institute of Asset
278 Management, 2015). Participants reported that handover information is primarily used to
279 comply with statutory-related inspections, such as fire alarm systems and electrical wiring
280 inspections.

281 Participants emphasised the repeated use of as-built drawings and product information for
282 the inspections of fire alarm systems. According to ID 65, having quality handover information
283 is crucial for managing all fire, life, and safety systems because it ensures statutory compliance
284 around all life and safety-related systems and ties in diversity. Supporting this view, ID 14 added
285 that *'fire alarm systems have been progressive and advanced, employing electronic devices and*
286 *components through sophisticated relays to provide a comprehensive coverage'*. Accordingly,
287 accurate handover information on the ancillary systems, such as lifts, is also necessary to conduct
288 *'comprehensive testing to ensure the safety of the building users in case of fire...fire [systems]*
289 *and lifts are tied together. So, it is legally obligated to inspect each lift from the integrated*
290 *system approach using a complete set of appropriate handover information'* (ID15).

291 Subsequently, managers of electrical systems asserted the importance of accurately
292 updated as-built drawings and equipment information for various mandated inspections (e.g., ID
293 27-30, 43, 44, 50, 52, 59, 61-64 & 94). ID 29 argued that *'electrical drawings reflecting the*
294 *precise locations of electrical gears and connecting wiring are required because equipment such*
295 *as MCC (Motor Control Centre) and UPS (Uninterruptible Power Supplies) can be installed*
296 *throughout the building or outside of the building.'* The detailed electrical site plans showing
297 precise locations of assorted electrical equipment, such as transformers, are indispensable for
298 managing a *'high voltage power network'*. Such power-supplying equipment carrying high
299 current demands stringent safety procedures before inspections. Accurately updating these plans,
300 especially after corrections and remedial work, is vital for ensuring safety in subsequent
301 inspections and future work (e.g., IDs 24, 27-30, 61, 62 & 64).

302 Similarly, as-built drawings and detailed product data are prerequisites for compliance
303 when operating a wide range of gas-fired equipment, such as boilers and water heaters. *'A set of*
304 *mechanical as-built drawings and product information are necessary to perform a yearly, bi-*
305 *annually, and full inspection of safety devices on the equipment'* (ID 31). Moreover, considering
306 the importance of inspecting the right equipment, the inspector regularly cross-references *'the*
307 *equipment plate information, including the make, model, and serial number, with the designated*
308 *equipment schedule and the associated mechanical drawings'* (ID 31).

309 Likewise, the participants consistently use a collection of plumbing plans and reliable
310 architectural floor plans for regular water quality testing and routine flush-out as required by
311 local safety regulations (IDs 40 & 42). The plumbing site and floor plans are typically used to
312 locate the building's main inlet and outlet for mandated Legionella testing. Those who manage
313 multiple buildings at remote sites use plumbing as-built drawings to pinpoint the sample
314 collection points for Legionella testing and establish the inspection plans for various buildings.
315 The architectural and plumbing floor plans are also commonly used to identify the locations of
316 plumbing fixtures for routine flushing. Therefore, ID 42 reiterated the significance of accurately
317 updated as-built plumbing drawings to regulate water quality-related issues.

318 *4.2. Organisational requirements*

319 Handover information is used to procure external contractors to perform ongoing
320 compulsory inspections. ID 35, for example, explains that *'a set of as-built drawings and*
321 *product information is necessary for solicitation purposes together with the narrative scope*
322 *of work in order to obtain right pricing'*. ID 14 noted that accurate handover information is
323 needed to understand *'your system's maintenance and testing requirements'*. Further, ID 29
324 argues that reliable electrical as-built drawings and trustworthy product information are
325 required for the contractors, ensuring the 'safety' of the workers when performing high-risk
326 equipment integrity inspections. For these reasons, the information quality dimensions of
327 'Accuracy' and 'Completeness' were highlighted in addition to updating the relevant drawings
328 and product information.

329 For internal compliance obligations, the building handover information is used for
330 managing the physical space. ID 1, for instance, relies on the building site plan, floor plans, and
331 room schedules to allocate, monitor, and audit space usage. Annual visual inspections validate
332 space assignments against floor plans, employee data or finance records of designated

333 departments. While 3-dimensional models are often lauded, , 2-dimensional drawings adequately
334 provide easy visualisations of the pertinent tasks. IDs 2, 6 and 9 focus on 'maximising existing
335 space usage under the guidelines of their organisations' internal compliance requirements due to
336 escalating capital investment costs. A comprehensive, accurate collection of spatial information
337 is preferred for effective management, exemplified by ID 9's practice of cross-referencing space
338 assignments with employee records to enhance the accuracy of the spatial information.

339 *4.3. Asset valuation for risk management*

340 Ongoing asset valuation involves assessing the building value based on different cost
341 elements, such as depreciation, operational, and replacement costs, because the value of a
342 building deteriorates over time (The Institute of Asset Management, 2015). The interviews,
343 however, uncovered that the primary purpose of asset valuation is to determine adequate
344 insurance coverage. Although there is no statutory obligation to purchase property insurance
345 policies, ID 11 noted, *'Organizations are generally risk-averse and want to transfer all risk to*
346 *an insurance policy and pay a premium. We don't, in general, assume any risks ourselves;*
347 *therefore, we have almost twenty different insurance policies to cover all types of risks.*
348 Consequently, participants reported obtaining insurance-related documents from handover
349 information. In some cases, insurance-required documents are included in the handover
350 information requirements (ID 3, 4, 13, 23, 35, 40, 61 & 62).

351 Professional quantity surveyors regularly use handover information to assess a
352 building's declared value, which is crucial in determining insurance coverage. This is essential
353 as some policies penalise for determining inadequate insurance premiums. IDs 1-3, 6 and 7
354 indicate that buildings and occupant details are also used for renewing liability insurance
355 policies every two years. Buildings with various functions often need multiple policies,
356 prompting insurance companies to conduct annual surveys. ID 12 noted, *'it does not demand a*
357 *set of handover information at the time of policy purchase, but it is recommended to have*
358 *accurately updated information available in the event of a claim in order to recover*
359 *replacement costs'.*

360 *4.4. Decision-making support for capital investment and operating expenditure*

361 For effective asset management, asset owners rely on various sources of information to
362 achieve the expected performance of assets. Asset owners make informed decisions on capital
363 investment and operating expenditure plans to attain this goal. In this context, handover

364 information provides essential information about the assets at different levels, supporting
365 effective decision-making. Although the decision-making process only partially depends on the
366 handover information, the interviews suggest that handover information can answer many
367 questions about existing systems and equipment within the building.

368 Participants indicated that handover information assists in making decisions related to
369 capital investment plans and operating expenditures to optimise asset lifespan in a commercial
370 building. IDs 74 and 76 elucidated the use of as-built drawings, technical specifications and
371 operation and maintenance manuals in capital project planning. They noted that *'the handover
372 information can answer many questions about the existing equipment when developing a scope
373 of work'*. The same participants also commented, *'construction documents and as-built
374 drawings, including engineering and operation and maintenance manuals of equipment, are
375 critical to making appropriate decisions for the assets, such as the modernisation, upgrade, and
376 replacement of existing systems'*. Several participants (e.g., IDs 7–13, 16, 33-40, 45-51, & 59-
377 63) concurred with this view. Furthermore, ID 65 and ID 71 shared experiences leveraging
378 handover information to detail technical specifications for the HVAC replacement project.

379 Transitioning from capital investment planning, the use of handover information is
380 extended to estimate operating expenses from an asset management perspective. Operating
381 expenses are typically estimated using various information, such as work order history and total
382 maintenance expenses. Participants (e.g., IDs 6,16, 23–30, 33, 36, 38, 40, 43, 52- 55, & 59-60)
383 specifically recognise the role of handover information in calculating these expenses in
384 multiple contexts. IDs 4 and 16 highlighted its role in forecasting operating outlays,
385 particularly for the buildings in overseas locations, where different operating strategies
386 necessitate reliance on handover information for budget establishment. Additionally, ID 75
387 employs as-built drawings to perform a financial pro forma for new spaces or buildings,
388 augmenting annual financial projects for future operational requirements. Furthermore, IDs 66
389 and 79 use specific architectural drawings such as floor plans, building elevations and site plans
390 to estimate for janitorial services, waste management, window cleaning and landscaping.

391 4.5. Preferred quality requirements for handover information

392 Figure 2 presents radar charts depicting the participants' quality preferences of handover
393 information that lead to desired outcomes. The charts indicate a preference for complete and
394 accurately updated handover information for effective task execution. 'Accuracy' emerged as a

395 key quality dimension, with some participants referring to it as 'Correctness' or 'Precision'
 396 depending on their area of expertise. For example, those managing physical space prioritised the
 397 accuracy of floor configurations over dimensional accuracy (e.g., IDs 1-5, 8 & 9). Accurate
 398 equipment details, such as the serial number and models, were vital, especially for ageing
 399 equipment, as handover information often contained outdated information. To counter this, some
 400 participants maintained duplicate, updated equipment records (e.g., IDs 15, 27, 31, 34, 52, & 61).
 401 Building location information was also deemed crucial by most participants, not just for safety
 402 but also for general liability insurance coverage. However, IDs 80-94 cautioned that the accuracy
 403 of handover information depends on the timing of its entry into asset management systems, as
 404 technological solutions cannot verify the information's accuracy.

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407 Figure 2. Handover Information Quality Preferences of the Selected Building Operations.

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Source: Authors' own creation/work.

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'Timeliness' emerged as another critical quality attribute, often described as up-to-date, updated, or the most updated information. Some participants used 'Timeliness' and 'Accuracy' interchangeably, emphasising that accurate information requires regular updates (IDs 80, 82, 84, 85, 87-89 & 93). Yet, the challenge of updating handover information for multiple buildings, particularly with minor ongoing projects, was noted (e.g., IDs 6, 7, 18, 19, 27-38, 47, 52, 54, 56, 61 & 62). To combat this, ID 6 noted, 'we've given our cleaning staff tablets so they

415 *can go around and record stuff that they find around site, take pictures of it, and then stick it*
416 *back in and we can keep up to date with damage and bits and pieces of the campus’.*

417 Following the emphasis on ‘Timeliness’ and ‘Accuracy’, ‘Completeness’ was also
418 identified as a critical quality dimension, with interpretations varying by expertise. For building
419 appraisals professionals, ‘Completeness’ entailed all graphical and non-graphical information
420 related to the building. Conversely, it meant for the participants involved in space management
421 was limited to site plans, floor layouts, furniture plans, and room schedules required to perform
422 their tasks effectively. For electrical, mechanical, fire alarm systems and lifts, complete
423 information includes relevant as-built drawings, detailed product information, and operation
424 and maintenance manuals (IDs 18, 20, 27, 30, 31, 33, 35, 36, 43, 44 & 64).

425 Based on the interviews, ‘Accuracy’, ‘Timeliness’, and ‘Completeness’ were identified as
426 the preferred quality dimensions of as-built drawings, product information, and installation
427 details in the Operation and Maintenance manuals to support effective asset management
428 processes. The quality dimensions of ‘Uniqueness’ were also merged during the interviews,
429 particularly concerning the addresses of buildings and other asset locations for the safety of
430 workers and occupants.

431 **5. Discussion**

432 The previous section reported evidence-based findings on the application of handover
433 information in the commercial building sector, illuminating the quality preferences derived from
434 participants’ experiences. This study emphasises the use of specific handover information, such
435 as drawings and various forms of non-graphical information. Intriguingly, participants had no
436 clear preference for either type in terms of enhancing building operations, presenting a
437 contrasting departure from findings in previous research. This divergence underscores the
438 complexity and varied perspectives in the building operations. Crucially, the efficacy of this
439 information depends on its ‘Accuracy’, ‘Timeliness’ and ‘Completeness’ to achieve the desired
440 outcomes in participants’ tasks. The insights drawn from this study point to a more intricate and
441 refined understanding of the significance and utilisation of various reliable handover information
442 forms in the efficient management of commercial buildings.

443 Interestingly, as-built drawings and product details are among the most frequently used
444 types of handover information. The interviews underscored the importance of accurate and
445 updated as-built drawings, illuminating the need for reliable spatial information in building

446 management. This includes the unique identification of buildings, particularly when managing
447 multiple properties to ensure the safety of employees and occupants. Additionally, as-built
448 drawings are instrumental in optimising space utilisation. Moreover, accurately locating various
449 equipment and non-addressable building support infrastructure is essential for compliance and
450 uninterrupted provision of building services. Unique identification, such as 10-digit codes, is
451 created to eliminate confusion arising from traditionally inherited building names. Further,
452 integrating Geographic Information System (GIS) coordinates enables tracking of outdoor assets,
453 extending even to remote locations (Kurwi *et al.*, 2021).

454 Product details, including manufacturers, models, serial numbers, and technical
455 specifications, are integral to optimising the expected life of assets at various levels (e.g.,
456 equipment and components). These details and as-built drawings are crucial for accurately
457 servicing and inspecting equipment in the correct locations and preparing insurance
458 documentation. Equipment product details are often cross-referenced to ensure accuracy with
459 asset tags and equipment schedules found in as-built drawings and asset registries. Besides, the
460 accurate technical specifications of assets are increasingly important, particularly in managing
461 the replacement of obsolete parts and components to prolong asset lifespan. Inaccuracies in
462 matching this specification can lead to significant system malfunctions, highlighting
463 obsolescence as a critical and growing concern in the building industry.

464 Combining the significance of as-built drawings and product details, this study can guide
465 the future development of BIM incorporating emerging technologies. This integration aims to
466 improve the quality of spatial information and its non-graphical counterparts. Participants have
467 identified that challenges associated with locating outdoor assets have been partly mitigated by
468 employing GIS to pinpoint the locations of buildings and exterior assets. This presents a
469 substantial opportunity to further improve handover information by integrating BIM with
470 cutting-edge technologies, such as the Indoor Positioning System (IPS) and Bluetooth Low-
471 Energy (BLE) beacons. This would precisely determine indoor positions and locations (Li,
472 Cheng and Chen, 2020). In addition, incorporating linked data into BIM could substantially
473 enhance the detail and accuracy of product information related to essential building equipment
474 and components (Farghaly *et al.*, 2019). This holistic approach addresses the needs identified by
475 the building management professionals for efficient operation and maintenance.

476 **6. Conclusions**

477 The empirical investigation of the use of building handover information and its quality
478 requirements in building management revealed several noteworthy findings. The study
479 underscores the critical role of handover information and its quality requisites for building
480 operations. Inferior quality handover information can compromise occupants' safety and obscure
481 ownership costs. The emphasis is on the need for a clear, reliable 'golden thread' of asset
482 information as mandated by regulations. Additionally, these findings enable asset owners to
483 identify specific handover information requirements in future building projects.

484 This study offers theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, this study
485 validates the proficiency of building management professionals in understanding handover
486 information requirements, challenging the previously held notion of a 'catch-all' approach by
487 building owners. This earlier approach was attributed to an unclear understanding of the
488 intended use of the information. Practically, this study affirms the critical role of handover
489 information in building operations, identifying specific areas where the use of inferior-quality
490 handover information can result in negative outcomes. This dual contribution enhances
491 understanding of the importance and practical implications of handover information in building
492 management.

493 Although this study has altered our understanding of handover information use, its
494 limitations must be recognised. The insights drawn from specific building sectors may not
495 represent all perspectives in building management. To strengthen the study's generalisability,
496 future research needs to broaden its scope and increase the sample size, incorporating a wider
497 variety of cases and participants. Such expansion would significantly enhance the reliability and
498 relevance. Future research should also focus on defining clear and specific information
499 requirements for BIM-based building management to further refine the understanding and
500 application of handover information.

501

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